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Deliverable D4.3 Quality Assurance Methodology and application in the first year

Deliverable D4.3

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Lead Partner: UPM

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Abstract

This Quality Assurance Principles is intended to support partners in the effective and efficient administration, procedural and financial management of the project. It focuses on project implementation procedures, structures and coordination and sets out key responsibilities for EU engagement and interaction. It is intended to support the achievement of project objectives, the effective management of partner progress and the timely delivery of project results.

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) on behalf of the EMAI4EU project

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Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Prepared by Name &Org.)	Approved by (WP-Leader)	Status
0.1	14/02/2024	Javier Segovia, Alberto Tejero, Mayte Sánchez	UPM	EITD	Draft
0.2	12/06/2024	Javier Segovia	UPM	Principles agreed with all partners in Town-Hall meeting 12/06/2024	Final version to comply with Milestone MS12.
0.3	10/11/2024	Mayte Sánchez	UPM		
0.4	20/11/2024	Alberto Tejero	UPM		
0.5	3/12/2024	Javier Segovia	UPM		
0.6	9/12/2024	Javier Segovia, Alberto Tejero, Mayte Sánchez	UPM		Sent to WP leaders
1.0	20/12/2024	Javier Segovia	UPM	EITD	
1.1	30/12/2025	Javier Segovia	UPM	EITD	Revision implementing PO Interim Review Feedback

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1 TASK 4.2 Quality assurance and harmonisation of curricula

Task 4.2 is described in the Grant Agreement contract, page 59:

This task foresees the development and deployment of specific quality control procedures to ensure that the project deliverables are peer-reviewed and revised by the consortium partners. The quality control procedures will be executed by the Quality Manager, while all other partners involved will have to enrol in a peer review rotation mechanism of the project's deliverables. The mechanism will be defined at the beginning of the project, agreed by all partners and Project Executive Committee. It will be presented in D4.3. This task will also focus on ensuring high-quality learning content of the education programmes delivered by EMAI4EU partners. The lead of this process is assigned to UPM, who will appoint a Quality Manager for the project. The harmonisation activities will involve regular meetings to make sure that the curricula of the master's programme will be developed following the same principles. Similar activities and regular meetings will also be carried out for harmonisation of the self-standing modules. The Quality Manager will monitor the quality of the education programmes via recurrent updates with WP1 Leader and WP2 Leader, who are responsible for the delivery of the EMAI4EU master's programme and self-standing learning modules. The quality of the programmes will be monitored via surveys and other dedicated activities to check with students about their satisfaction in relation to the content and format of the education programmes.

Deliverable D4.1, Project Management Handbook, also refers to Quality Assurance:

2.1.5 The Quality Manager (QM): the QM is responsible for the definition of the Quality Assurance Plan and its implementation by all partners. The QM will manage and coordinate the procedures to assess the quality of project deliverables and learning content for the short-term training programmes, appointing peer reviewers from the partners' staff to support the process.

5 Quality Control: With regards to quality assurance and monitoring, the Quality Manager (QM) will be responsible for establishment and guiding implementation of quality assurance procedures. Quality processes include the timely completion and review of all technical achievements (deliverables, milestones) compared to the original time plan, as described in the Grant Agreement contract, and learning content for the education programmes. The QM will ensure that the periodic activity, deliverable, management, and final project reports are completed and of high quality in accordance with the work plan. Additionally, the QM will keep the PEC informed on the status of all active quality processes and raise any issues requiring remedial action. As required, the QM takes part in PEC meetings as required and reports directly to the GEA. Additionally, the QM will ensure that the learning content used by the training providers is of high quality. The QM will keep the relevant WP Leaders and Task Leaders updated on the development status of the short-term training programmes from each training providers and raise any issues requiring urgent action. The definition of an effective quality monitoring system and mechanism will allow to monitor the phases

of the project, to understand if the project is proceeding as planned and to anticipate problems instead of solving them afterwards. The quality control mechanism will overlook the project deliverables production and learning content production, relying on the expertise of the QM. The procedure that will be followed for the preparation of deliverables and production of the learning content will be agreed at the very beginning of the project. Before submission or publication, each project deliverable and learning content will be reviewed by the QM. When appropriate, the document/material will also undergo an English check by a native speaker.

Following the above description of the task, and the instructions given at deliverable D4.1 Project Management Handbook, the Quality Assurance Team prepared the Definition of a Quality Assurance Principles, due as MS12 in Month 6. The Principles were agreed with all partners in Town-Hall meeting 12/06/2024.

The following sections will describe the Quality Assurance Plan, and the methodology and artefacts created and how they were applied during this first year of the project.

2 Quality Assurance Plan

With regards to quality assurance and monitoring, the Quality Manager (QM) will be responsible for establishment and guiding implementation of quality assurance procedures as a Quality Assurance Plan (QAP). It is very important to highlight that QAP is related both to the project processes and deliverables.

Regarding the project processes, the main objectives of the QAP are to:

- Monitor the project progress.
- Ensure the quality completeness of each activity and output separately and of the whole project.
- Ensure the quality of the key processes and the key results of the project.
- Identify possible bottlenecks and enable corrective activity.

QAP processes include the timely completion and review of all processes and technical achievements (deliverables, milestones) compared to the original time plan, as described in the Grant Agreement contract, and learning content for the education programmes.

The QAP ensure that the periodic activity, deliverable, management, and final project reports are completed and of high quality in accordance with the work plan. Additionally, the QM will keep the Project Executive Committee (PEC) informed on the status of all active quality processes and raise any issues requiring remedial action. As required, the QM takes part in PEC meetings as required and reports directly to the General Assembly (GEA). Section 3 of this deliverable, *Project Progress Quality Assurance*, is devoted to this part of the QAP.

As stated in section 1, the QAP also included monitoring the quality of the education programmes, ensuring that the learning content used by the training providers is of high quality. Regarding this, the QAP contains two activities related to it:

- the Academic QA activity related to WP1, focused on the deployment of the EMAI4EU master's programme in Artificial Intelligence, with a specialization in Emotion AI and a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship
- The Self standing learning Modules QA activity related to WP2, focused on developing and delivering all self-standing modules and related certification schemes.

Section 4, *Learning Content Production Quality Assurance*, is devoted to this academic part of the QAP.

The definition of an effective quality control and monitoring system and mechanism will allow to monitor the phases of the project, to understand if the project is proceeding as planned and to anticipate problems instead of solving them afterwards. The QAP uses a couple of artefacts¹:

- Quality Checklists to collect and organize the marks needed to hit during the project. At each section we will describe the checklist used. Checklists include references to evidence, when applicable.
- A Risk Management Plan consisting of the identification of the academical and management risks; the assessment of their degree of occurrence, and of their potential impact; and of reducing the possibility of materialisation for each one of the risks already foreseen in the design of the project by planning the necessary mitigation measures to be taken during implementation.

This way the quality control mechanism will overlook the project deliverables production and learning content production, relying on the expertise of the QM.

The procedure that we followed for the preparation of deliverables and production of the learning content is described at deliverable D4.1 Project Management Handbook.

2.1 Contact Information

For general questions regarding the Quality Assurance Plan, contact Javier Segovia (javier.segovia@upm.es)

For specific questions regarding Quality Assurance in Project Progress, contact Mayte Sanchez (mayte.sanchez@ctb.upm.es)

For specific questions regarding Learning Content Production Quality Assurance in WP1, contact Javier Segovia (javier.segovia@upm.es)

¹ Based on the "*PM² Methodology*" originated from the European Commission, supported as an initiative by Digital Europe Programme https://pm2.europa.eu/index_en

For specific questions regarding Learning Content Production Quality Assurance in WP2, contact Alberto Tejero (alberto.tejero@upm.es)

3 Project Progress Quality Assurance

Quality Assurance activities² will be performed by evaluating the design of project controls, by confirming that they are implemented, and by assessing their operational effectiveness. They will ensure that the following management activities are taking place:

- The Management structure is defined
- The Project contacts list is available
- Regarding the preparation and organization of meetings, at GEA, PEC or WP level, ordinary or extraordinary
 - The Convening meeting's agenda exists
 - The Meetings are organized in due time
 - The Notice of meetings are sent with the agenda
 - The Minutes of meetings are sent on time
 - The Documentation presented at the meetings is available
- Regarding the Decision-Making Process
 - There is a Project's List of Decisions Taken extracted and sorted by topics from the minutes
 - The Issues and agreements reached to solve them are included in the above list
- The Project Milestones are reached
- A Risk analysis, identification, and mitigation measures by each WP is produced in a Risk management plan

Various *Project Progress Quality Checklist* were developed to control and monitor the status of the project progress:

- QA Deliverable Checklist
- QA Milestone Checklist
- QA Meetings Checklist
- QA Risks Matrix

² Based on the "*PM² Methodology*" originated from the European Commission, supported as an initiative by Digital Europe Programme https://pm2.europa.eu/index_en

3.1 Deliverables Production and Review Process

All AMEI4EU partners has a responsibility to deliver high quality deliverables in a timely and appropriate manner, being the Project Coordinator (PC) the ultimately responsible for the quality control of the deliverables to the European Commission (EC), always with a close coordination with the project steering committee and the quality assurance committee (QAC).

All project deliverables are associated with a specific work package task. The Quality Manager (QM) is responsible for overseeing the deliverable review process from start to finish, setting review timelines, and supporting both peer reviewers and the Deliverable Team throughout the process. The Deliverable Team is composed of the WP and Task leaders. The WP leaders are in charge of the production of project deliverables, and of the reporting of the status of the deliverables to the PEC. The Task leaders will contribute to the deliverables connected to their tasks. It will be the responsibility of the Task leaders to co-ordinate the drafting of the deliverable and ensure the inputs of other partners where necessary.

Every contractual deliverable, prior to its submission to the EC will also be shared with all partners within the respective WP for an internal peer review.. The partners involved in the WP will act as peer-reviewers, as expert partners different from ones that created the implied deliverable, and will review and check the document for the overall quality of contents, presentation, comprehensiveness, etc We opted to involve all partners in the review process—rather than limiting it to just two peer reviewers as initially outlined in the Grant Agreement—because this approach promotes collective responsibility for the deliverable’s quality and accuracy, while also encouraging active participation and alignment with the project’s objectives. The Project Manager (PM) will perform a final check, being responsible of the submission and final approval of deliverables.

D4.1 Project Management Handbook describe the conventions regarding the deliverable and version control template to be used by all partners, the file naming convention, etc.

Deliverable progress is monitored by the use of the following checklist-

NOTE: colour codes used in the checklist

- Del. column: violet means that the document must be submitted during the current project period.
- Status column: red means that the document needs significant changes after review, yellow means it needs minor changes, and green means the document is correct.

DELIVERABLES LIST, PEER REVIEWERS AND DATES

Del.	Deliverable name	Due Date	WP	Leader	Due for deliverable report	Reviewer and due date 1st revision	Status	Due Coordinator Revision and submission to EC	Submitted date
D1.1.	EMAI4EU master's programme: Market analysis and curriculum design	M13 (31/01/2025)	WP1	UCA	10/01/2025				
D1.2	Report on EMAI4EU master's programme delivery - Academic Year 2024/2025	M30 (30/06/2026)	WP1	POLIMI	01/06/2026				
D1.3	Report on EMAI4EU master's programme delivery - Academic Year 2025/2026	M42 (30/06/2027)	WP1	UPM	01/06/2027				
D1.4	Report on EMAI4EU master's programme delivery - Academic Year 2026/2027	M54 (30/06/2028)	WP1	ELTE	01/06/2028				
D2.1	EMAI4EU self-standing modules: Market analysis and curriculum design	M22 (31/10/2025)	WP2	UTU	01/10/2025				
D2.2	Intermediate report on delivery of EMAI4EU self-standing learning modules	M38 (28/02/2027)	WP2	UNITN	04/12/2026				

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D2.3	Final report on delivery of EMAI4EU self-standing learning modules	M54 (30/06/2028)	WP2	UNITN	05/12/2027				
D3.1	Marketing and Dissemination Plan	M6 (30/06/2024)	WP3	EITD	01/06/2024	UPM-12/06/2024		20/06/2024	
D3.2	Report on marketing and dissemination activities - Year 1	M18 (30/06/2025)	WP3	EITD	01/06/2025				
D3.3	Report on marketing and dissemination activities - Year 2	M30 (30/06/2026)	WP3	UR1	01/06/2026				
D3.4	Report on marketing and dissemination activities - Year 3	M42 (30/06/2027)	WP3	EITD	01/06/2027				
D3.5	Report on marketing and dissemination activities - Year 4	M54 (30/06/2028)	WP3	UR1	01/06/2028				
D4.1	Project Management Handbook	M6 (30/06/2024)	WP4	EITD	01/06/2024	UPM-12/06/2024		20/06/2024	
D4.2	Data Management Plan	M6 (30/06/2024)	WP4	EITD	01/06/2024	UPM-12/06/2024		20/06/2024	
D4.3	Quality Assurance Methodology and application in the first year	M12 (31/12/2024)	WP4	UPM	09/12/2024	EIT-18/12/2024		30/12/2024	
D4.4	Enrolment to EMAI4EU education programmes and scholarship allocation– Results (Year 1)	M12 (31/12/2024)	WP4	EITD	18/11/2024	XXX-15/11/2024		15/12/2024	
D4.5	Enrolment to EMAI4EU education programmes and scholarship allocation– Results (Year 2)	M24 (31/12/2025)	WP4	EITD	17/11/2025				
D4.6	Enrolment to EMAI4EU education programmes – Results (Year 3)	M36 (31/08/2027)	WP4	EITD	01/07/2027				
D4.7	Enrolment to EMAI4EU education programmes – Results (Year 4)	M54 (30/06/2028)	WP4	EITD	01/06/2028				

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D4.8	Quality Assurance application in Academic Year 2024/2025	M24 (31/12/2025)	WP4	UPM	17/11/2025				
D4.9	Quality Assurance application in Academic Year 2025/2026	M36 (31/12/2026)	WP4	UPM	16/11/2026				
D4.10	Quality Assurance application in Academic Year 2026/2027	M54 (30/06/2028)	WP4	UPM	01/06/2028				
D4.11	Intermediate Report on community, partnership, and mobility management	M30 (30/06/2026)	WP4	EITD	01/06/2026				
D4.12	Final report on community, partnership, and mobility management	M54 (30/06/2028)	WP4	EITD	01/06/2028				

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3.2 QA Milestone Checklist

Internal evaluations will assess the EMAI4EU's progress and identify any necessary corrective measures and actions if there is insufficient progress. Among others, evaluation of the project will be based on the grade of achievement of milestones. The following section describes the artefact used to monitor the progress of achievement of milestones.

The following checklist was created to indicate and monitor the degree of achievement of each milestone and the associated comments.

NOTE: colour codes used in the checklist

- MS achieved. column: green means that the milestone was achieved

MS	Milestone	Associated WP	Lead Beneficiary	Scheduled Deadline	Means of verification	Adapted Milestone (date or/and grade of achievement)	deviation %	MS achieved
MS1	Tentative curriculum of the master's programme defined	WP1	5-ELTE	M3	Documentation collected and uploaded to the EMAI4EU data repository.			YES
MS2	Labour market needs analysis completed, and curriculum of the master's programme finalised	WP1	2-UCA	M10	Approval by all partners of the final curriculum of the master's programme.			YES
MS3	First two-year cycle of the master's programme delivered	WP1	1-EITD	M40	Graduation and awarding of doubledegree titles to students completing the full cycle of the			

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					master's programme			
MS4	Second two-year cycle of the master's programme delivered	WP1	5-ELTE	M52	Graduation and awarding of double degree titles to students completing the full cycle of the master's programme.			
MS5	Self-standing learning modules and related certification schemes completed	WP2	4-UTU	M21	Full curriculum of self-standing learning modules completed and available online.			
MS6	First annual cycle of certification exams completed	WP2	3-INUTN	M40	Certification exams completed and certifications released to successful participants.			
MS7	Second annual cycle of certification exams completed	WP2	3-INUTN	M52	Certification exams completed and certifications released to successful participants.			
MS8	Development of a Marketing and Dissemination Plan	WP3	1-EITD	M4	A detailed written Marketing and Dissemination Plan shared with and rolled out in cooperation with the consortium.			YES

					Active website (regular updates).			
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As we can see, all Milestones due in the first year of the project were reached on time.

3.3 QA Meetings Checklist

As described in D4.1 Project Management Handbook, the following meetings will be called regularly.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly (GEA)	Four meetings: 1 st - within first three month of year 1, 2 nd - within second half of year 2, 3 rd - within second half of year 3, 4 th - within second half of year 4.	At any time upon request of the Project Executive Committee or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Project Executive Committee (PEC)	Monthly teleconferences. Face-to-face meeting organize every 6 months: in March and September of each project year.	At any time upon request of any Member of the General Assembly
General Assembly and Project Executive Committee	GEA and PEC will meet jointly at the beginning of the project for detailed strategy and planning.	
Work Package (WP)	Monthly for each WP.	At any time upon request of any Member of the WP or Project Coordinator

To monitor the progress of the meetings, we devised templates to describe the agenda and the minutes generated in each meeting. The following is an example of how it was used in the KOM:

EMAI4EU Project Kick-off meeting

Brussels, 12 February 2024

Minutes

MEETING NOTES			
Type of meeting	Kick-off	Date	2024 02 12
Meeting Objectives	1) Presentation of partners	Time	9:30 h
	2) Setting the goals and project objectives	Location	EIT House, Rue Guilmard 7, 4 th floor, 1000 Brussels, Belgium
	3)		

Attendees
26 in person <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salvatore Moccia, Andrea Biancini, Olivia Pantea, Federico Guerrini, Christian Sjostrom (EITD) Marta Patino, Javier Segovia, Alberto Tejero (UPM) Laszlo Gulyas (ELTE) Raphael Troncy (EURECOM) Federico Schlegatti, Gianluca Palermo, Davide Martinenghi (POUMI) Tapio Pahikkala (UTU) Alvaro Pina Stranger, Stephanie Gauvain (UR) Francoise Baude, Guilhem Lecouteux (UCA) Luigi Palopoli (UniTn) Nicola Tardelli, Andrea Prina (MED/SPA) Eric Lasier, Robin Petit (LUDOTIC) Juan Manuel Depcich (TECHVALLEY) Natalia Rodriguez (SATURNOLABS)
5 online: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elin Karlsson, (EITD) Jean Martinet, Jean Piroddi (UCA) Teresa Colombi, Sebastien Chalme (LUDOTIC)

EMAI4EU MEETING NOTES/DISCUSSION AND ACTIONS TO BE TAKEN
EMAI4EU Project General Introduction & Reporting The meeting opened with an introduction led by Prof. Salvatore Moccia, EITD EMAI4EU Coordinator and Head of Master School, giving an overview of the project and the context in which, it develops and implements. Each member of the Consortium gave a short introduction of who they are, which partner university they represent and what role they have in the project. Project Officer notes ad key project elements Maria Gkontouma (HADEA, EC) provided a presentation regarding the main formal aspect to manage the project correctly and to guarantee achievement of project results.
WP1 – Master's programmes T1.1. Market Analysis and curriculum development

The WP1, Task 1. was introduced by Jean Martinet, UCA, Task 1.1 Leader.
 The first activities to be started regards the creation of a labor market analysis to provide input for the curriculum definition. In the project there are two milestones defined about this topic:
 - M3: first draft of what we would like to deliver
 - M10: labor market needs analysis completed
 All partners are involved in this task, with different PMs, and have the opportunity to contribute to it.

 The next actions for all are basically two:
 1. Universities provide info on similar courses from their institutions or others they are aware of.
 2. Industrial partners provide info on job market needs moving from services to be deployed and/or workforce needs.

Adjustments of this curriculum will continue, after market analysis, from M7 to M10. Possibly all curricula will be defined before October 24 (M10). This will give us the opportunity to start the first recruitment cycle in November 2024 and get first students in the academic year 2025/2025.

T1.2. Delivery of the master's programme in Emotion AI
 The WP1, Task 2. was introduced by Laszlo Gulyas, ELTE, WP1 Leader and Task 1.2 Leader supported by Luigi Palopoli, UniTn.

Regarding the structure of the master, we agreed this high level organization:
 Year 1:
 - I&E (I&E electives 9 ECTS): 24 ECTS
 - Mandatory AI/CS courses/emotion: 30 ECTS
 - Free choice (CS/Engineer): 6 ECTS

Summer school cannot be budgeted in EMAI4EU, so they cannot contribute to the 120 ECTS.
 As suggested by the PO, we can just add it as a self-standing module and realize it without providing ECTS that contribute to the 120 ECTS of the EMAI4EU master.
 To defend the distinctive value of our masters, we would keep the Summer School mandatory for all students. Since the 4 ECTS recognized by this school could not concur to the 120 ECTS required for the master programme, we need to consider in the curriculum design a 4 ECTS "carrier course" to cover the missing ECTS from the Summer School. This course could be a course with a "common name" in all local instances of the program (for example, "I&E for Venture Creation") in the I&E minor. This course will be used by each university to insert the grades from the Summer School.

Year 2:
 - I&E (I&E study related to EA), challenges shared) 6 ECTS
 - Mandatory Emotion (specializations) 18 ECTS
 - Free choice (CS/Engineer) 6 ECTS
 - Internship/Thesis 30 ECTS

The different universities still need to agree on:
 - Which are the core competences we want (they should be in the mandatory part in Year 1).
 - Specialization: Emotional AI will be the specialization, each university can give a sort of flavor to it (like neurologist...).

Regarding core components, the members of the consortium started agreeing on this list:
 - Machine learning 1 (KNN, clustering, ...): 6 ECTS
 - Machine learning 2 (deep learning): 6 ECTS
 - Multimodal Signal Processing (Natural Language, or Signal, or Vision): 6 ECTS

- Natural Language (BASICS)
- Neuro signal processing
- Computer vision

 - Programming 6 ECTS
 - ...

Every university will continue independently this exercise by refining the module list and mapping them with the internal courses, to also check the internal constraints regarding entry/exit year prerequisites.
WP2 – Self standing learning modules T2.1. Market analysis and modules development Market analysis will be done together with the one in WP1, T1.1. T2.2. Delivery of the self-standing learning modules Andrea Biancini, EITD, Project Manager provided an overview of this activity and its goals. These modules should aim at many new learners and provide online and hybrid learning activities. We need to create learning paths providing entry- and expert-level courses. During the project we will work to put together a structure of this self-standing modules. The modules can be published on a platform provided by EIT Digital (Nectarios). The platform offers the possibility to translate the course in all the 27 languages simultaneously. EITD will arrange a demo for this platform. Together with online modules the project will provide a certification scheme. We need to agree who will release the certificate (if it will be the partner university or EIT Digital) and which will be the certification paths. Salvatore Moccia, EITD, Project Coordinator raised also the idea of providing a upskilling wallet where potential learners will have an amount (just for example, let's say €100) that they can spend on the platform to do courses and certifications.
WP3 – Marketing and Dissemination T3.1. Marketing and promotion activities Olivia Pantea, EITD, WP3 Leader presented the guidelines for branding and the main activities done in marketing and promotion. EMAI4EU has a logo, which was presented to all partners, and a website (https://www.eitdigital.eu/en/collaborations/emai4eu/). Regarding communication activities on the master, the partner universities opened a discussion on the prerequisites to enroll to the master. There was an agreement to lower the prerequisite to 45 ECTS in CS (instead of 60) and 20 in math (instead of 30), for example. An additional specification can then be added regarding the fact that entry/exit universities can reject admissions based on competitive criteria. To further refine these prerequisites, all universities will share information regarding the ECTS provided in their bachelor programme so that a minimum number of ECTS can be sort out of it. The goal is to give at least a full possibility to apply to the program to all students of the bachelor programs of the partner universities. The audience for self standing modules will be wider, including all people of 16+ age and even without any specific education level.
T3.2. Dissemination and communication activities This activity will be led by Alvaro Stranger, UR, T3.2 Leader.
WP4 - Project management and education programme administration T4.3. Enrolment and scholarship programme administration Elin Karlsson, EITD, T4.3 Leader described the process for enrollment of students to the master program. We foresee 3 periods of admissions for each cycle.

Scholarships, for EMAI4EU will be of three kinds:
 1. scholarships of excellence (consisting of full tuition fee waivers and a monthly allowance paid to the student: ~800€/month, adapted by a coefficient adapted to the host country life-cost, for the duration of the master),
 2. full tuition fee waivers (the scholarship will cover all tuition fees for the student), and
 3. half tuition fee waivers (the scholarship will cover 50% of the tuition fees for the student).

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The meetings progress was annotated in the following Meeting Checklist, with information regarding this first year 2024.

N.	Ordinary Meeting	Extraordinary meeting	Date	Has the meeting been held?	Have meeting notes been taken?	Related documents
1	Kick-off Meeting		12 th February 2024	YES	YES	-20240212_EMAI4EU_Kick-off Meeting Minutes.docx -20240112 EMAI4EU_Kick-off Meeting Agenda.docx -20240212 EMAI4EU_Kick-off Meeting Attendance List.docx -20240212 EMAI4EU_Kick-off Meeting Presences.pdf
2	PEC meeting		2nd April 2024	YES	YES	-20240402 EMAI4EU_PEC and project meeting Minutes.docx -20240402 EMAI4EU_PEC and project meeting.pptx
3	Townhall meeting		12th June 2024	YES	YES	-20240612 EMAI4EU_Townhall meeting Agenda.docx -20240612 EMAI4EU_Townhall meeting Minutes.docx -20240612 EMAI4EU_Townhall meeting.pptx - 20240612EMAI4EU_Townhallmeeting_2024_06_T1.1_UCA.pptx - 20240612_Townhallmeeting_MSM12 QualityPrinciplesMilestones.pdf
4	WP1 biweekly meeting		18 January 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024 0118.docx

5	WP1 biweekly meeting		29 February 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024 0229.docx
6	WP1 biweekly meeting		07 March 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024030 7.docx
7	WP1 biweekly meeting		02 April 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024040 2.docx
8	WP1 biweekly meeting		16 April 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024041 6.docx
9	WP1 biweekly meeting		30 April 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024043 0.docx
10	WP1 biweekly meeting		28 May 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024052 8.docx
11	WP1 biweekly meeting		11 June 2024	YES	YES	- EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_DATE_2024061 1.docx
12	WP1 biweekly meeting		25 June 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240625.docx
13	WP1 biweekly meeting		09 July 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240709.docx
14	WP1 biweekly meeting		23 July 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240723.docx
15	WP1 biweekly meeting		30 July 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240730.docx
16	WP1 biweekly meeting		27 August 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240827.docx
17	WP1 biweekly meeting		03 Septemb er 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240903.docx

18	WP1 biweekly meeting		06 Septemb er 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240906.docx
19	WP1 biweekly meeting		17 September 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240917.docx
20	PEC monthly meeting		24 September 2024	YES	YES	-20240924_EMAI4EU_PEC-meeting- Minutes.docx
21	WP1 biweekly meeting		27 September 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20240927.docx
22	WP1 biweekly meeting		11 October 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241011.docx
23	WP1 biweekly meeting		18 October 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241018.docx
24	WP1 biweekly meeting		25 October 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241025.docx
25	PEC monthly meeting		29 October 2024	YES	YES	-20241029_EMAI4EU_PEC-meeting- Minutes.docx
26	WP1 biweekly meeting		08 November 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241108.docx
27	WP2 KOM		14 November 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP2_20241114.docx
28	WP1 biweekly meeting		22 November 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241122.docx
29	PEC monthly meeting		26 November 2024	YES	YES	-20241126_EMAI4EU_PEC-meeting- Minutes.docx
30	WP1 biweekly meeting		06 December 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241206.docx

31	WP1 biweekly meeting		20 December 2024	YES	YES	-EMAI4EU_Minutes_WP1_20241220.docx
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A total of 31 meetings were held during 2024.

It is noteworthy that the WP1 meetings, initially planned as monthly, have been held biweekly instead, as indicated in the checklist above. These meetings are intended to monitor the progress of WP1, so no agendas are generated, and the list of attendees is included in the minutes.

Regarding WP2, the Kick-Off Meeting was held online on November 14th, 2024. Although WP2 officially starts in M1, the online courses need to be developed during the second year. The first year is dedicated to market analysis, which will be conducted in synergy with a similar task in WP1. The collaboration between WP1 and WP2 activities and the communication among project members suggested that joint meetings for WP1 and WP2 would be beneficial. This approach was followed until November 2024, after which WP2 scheduled its own regular monthly meetings.

For WP3, the WP leader (EITD) holds regular meetings with the internal back office (involved in marketing and student enrolment) and with the Marketing and Communication team to discuss plans regarding marketing and enrolment statistics. Minutes are not taken for these meetings.

Regarding the PEC monthly meetings, they were scheduled for the latter part of the year after the initial period and began in September 2024.

These actions of preparation and organization of meetings are directly related to risk ID-2, which will be discussed in the next section.

3.4 Risks Matrix of Foreseen Risks

This section presents the risk management strategy and processes of EMAI4EU. EMAI4EU is a complex project in a dynamic environment, between different entities, universities, European institutions, SMEs, and other related initiatives and networks. To ensure the goals of the project, certain risks to the project's success needs to be handled in a structured and timely manner.

The process and structure for managing risks strategy will ensure an early identification of certain risks within the implementation and monitoring of the project. The goal of the risk management processes is that project risks are identified, analysed, evaluated, and treated in a structured process that monitors and tracks them, and raises risks to the right level and responsibilities in the project.

The following risk tracking tools have been created:

- A Risk Log to keep track of all known risks and to follow on risk responses.
- An Issue Log to describe project issues and mitigation actions put in place.

Regular reviews lead us to the identification of new risks, review the existing ones, adaptation of risk level assessments, adapting risk response strategy and mitigation actions. Periodic updates are the basis of checking and adapting risks, mitigation, severity and also imminence.

Risk identification, analysis, evaluation and decisions and final treatment could be the steps in the risk management plan. This report will be updated according to the risks detailed in the General Agreement document.

The risks identified in the EMAI4EU proposal are shown in the table below:

Risk Number	Description	Work Package	Proposed Mitigation Measures
ID1	Key deliverables, milestones delayed due to disagreement or purpose. Likelihood: Low	WP3; WP4, WP1, WP2	The Description of Actions to be performed is drafted in the clearest way in the Grant Agreement. In case of disagreement, a conflict resolution process is initiated
ID2	Failure to recognise linkages between tasks, and critical paths. Likelihood: Low	WP3; WP4, WP1, WP2	Regular online meetings within and between WPs are planned to ensure that linkages are identified and strengthened
ID3	To produce high-quality results, the consortium will have to dedicate more efforts, corresponding to a higher budget. Likelihood: Low.	WP3; WP4, WP1, WP2	Advanced monitoring mechanisms will be put in place by the Project Manager to track the resources spent. All consortium partners are experienced in this field, being used to work efficiently in organisations that have sufficient resources to predict the amount of work to perform within the time limit of the project.
ID4	During the definition of the curricula of the master's programme, the courses offered by one of the higher education institutions do not have learning outcomes aligned with the courses offered by another institution. Likelihood: Low.	WP1	A tentative curriculum of the courses offered in the master's programme by each partner (see Section 4) has been defined at proposal stage to avoid this issue as much as possible. Shall this issue arise during the finalisation of the curricula, a conflict resolution process will be initiated (see Section 2.3.2) by WP1/WP2 Leader with the support of the Project Coordinator if required.
ID5	The understanding process of the needs of the labour markets does not provide enough significant information to find an agreement on the target audience of the self-	WP2	The approach to understand the labour market needs will integrate various methods (e.g. surveys) and diverse sources to analyse relevant literature and gather data from the labour market, also leveraging on the SMEs part of EMAI4EU consortium and industry partners in the EITD ecosystem. In case that one of the methods does not

	learning modules. Likelihood: Medium		provide the required information, they will complement with each other
ID6	Lack of participation to some of the education programmes. Likelihood: Medium	WP1, WP2	Thanks to the preparation work carried out in the context of WP1 and WP2 to define education curricula that are market-relevant, the education programmes will be very well aligned with the needs of the labour market, especially the ones from the 7 EMAI4EU
ID7	Key deliverables and milestones related to the development and deployment of education programmes delayed due to external factors such as health crisis. Likelihood: Low	WP1, WP2	All higher education institutions in the consortium are available to adjust the course format and have learnt a lot in the past couple of years during the COVID-19 pandemic. As an extreme measure, in order to achieve the desired impact, the delivery of the some of the face-to-face courses envisaged as part of the master's programme will be done in online format.
ID8	Marketing and promotion campaigns does not allow to reach the target audience and generate new leads. Likelihood: Medium	WP3	A multi-channel marketing strategy will be put in place, involving coordinated promotion activities from all partners, especially the business/professional associations. This strategy will allow to understand which channels are most effective to reach the target audience. These channels will be prioritised, while channels that will be underperforming over time will be discontinued.
ID9	Lack of consensus in the definition of the scholarship programmes. Likelihood: Low	WP4	The scholarship programmes to target different people in needs and to promote diversity has been already discussed by the Project Coordinator with the consortium during the preparation of EMAI4EU project proposal. Shall any issue arise during the duration of the project, an clear decision-making system will be put in place since the early stage of the project to take decisions.

A EMAI4EU Risk Matrix was generated from the proposal. The QA team elaborated an Impact index, from 0 to 5, so that an Impact 0 means that there is no damage to the project, and an Impact of 5 means an extreme damage. From those levels of likelihood (1 very low, 2 low, 3 medium, 4 high, 5 very high) of the risk and the impact, we calculated a Risk Intensity, multiplying the likelihood of the risk with its impact, as the table below shows together with the matrix (colour reflecting the Intensity).

ID Risk	ikelihood (L)	Impact (I)	Risk intensity (IxL)
ID 1	2	5	10
ID 2	2	4	8
ID 3	2	5	10
ID 4	2	4	8
ID 5	3	4	12
ID 6	3	4	12
ID 7	2	3	6
ID 8	2	4	8
ID 9	3	3	9

In the graph, green means low Risk Intensity, yellow medium, and red maximum

The above matrix and graph reflect the starting point of the project.

Every year a new matrix is generated, indicating whether the risk intensity has changed during the execution of the project. The following reflects the change after one year of the project:

ID Risk	ikelihood (l)	Impact (I)	Risk intensity (IxL)
ID 1	1	5	5
ID 2	3	4	12
ID 3	2	5	10
ID 4	1	4	4
ID 5	1	4	4
ID 6	1	4	4
ID 7	2	3	6
ID 8	2	4	8
ID 9	3	3	9

For example, risk ID 1 has decreased because all deliverables and milestones were reached on time. Similarly, ID 4, ID 5, and ID 6 have also decreased due to the Learning Content Production Quality Assurance processes, which resulted in a curriculum for the master's program that is well-aligned with the learning outcomes and market needs (see section 4).

However, risk ID 2 has changed from low to medium risk, with its intensity increasing from 8 to 12. This is because the likelihood (y-axis) has risen by up to 3 points due to changes done with some of the meetings of PEC, WP2, and WP3 (see section 3.3). The QA team raised the Risk ID 2 level as a precautionary measure, not because it was perceived as a significant risk. The decisions made regarding those meetings seemed justified, and the plan moving forward is to hold the meetings as originally scheduled in all WPs.

3.5 Unforeseen Risks

The Risks Log includes also unforeseen risks. The following unforeseen risks have also been detected during review period (1):

- U1: The need to efficiently manage the distribution of scholarships within the EIT Digital ecosystem required a structured and legally compliant approach.
- U2: The open call for scholarships on the Cycle 1 of the EMAI4EU master has been opened and assigned but it was not registered on the Funding and Tender portal right from the first recruitment period (one of three periods).
- U3: During the first 15 months of the project, EITD experienced a change in the WP3 lead position, slowing down the continuity of work.

A description of these risks, their possible impact in the project, and the applied mitigation measures, can be found in the document EMAI4EU Periodic Report (Part A and B), section “Critical risks and risk management strategy”.

4 Learning Content Production Quality Assurance

4.1 Definition of a Quality Assurance Principles

In order to define the Academic QA plan and activities, we must first choose some principles to follow. This goal was the subject of Milestone MS12, Definition of a Quality Assurance Principles, with the following description:

Creation of a quality principles to ensure that education programmes are of high quality and developed according to common principles

The Milestone is related to the following references at the proposal:

- *Page 20, EMAI4EU Implementation plan | Master's programme: The master's programme will be developed following the same principles and will have the same structure*
- *Page 21, EMAI4EU Implementation plan | Self-Standing on-line Modules: Although developed by different organisations, all modules will be built and delivered following common principles. Harmonisation of the curricula and formats of the modules will be ensured by the leaders of Task 1.2 and Task 2.2, and by the overarching activities carried out within Task 4.2... Common principles will be applied not only during the design and development phase, but also during the delivery phase.*
- *Page 60, Task 4.2: The harmonisation activities will involve regular meetings to make sure that the curricula of the master's programme will be developed following the same principles. Similar activities and regular meetings*

will also be carried out for harmonisation of the self-standing modules. The Quality Manager will monitor the quality of the education programmes via recurrent updates with WP1 Leader and WP2 Leader, who are responsible for the delivery of the EMAI4EU master's programme and self-standing learning modules

- Page 46, T1.1: Adjust the tentative master's programme curriculum based on the knowledge from other partners and final mapping of the labour market needs in Emotion AI – M7-M10
- Page 47, T1.1: The final aim of this task is to create a curriculum of the master's programme that reflect the needs of the labour market in AI and the specific needs in relation to future applications of Emotion AI technology.
- Page 51, T2.1: Define the self-learning programme curriculum based on the identified labour market needs

In order to follow those mandates, we decided to apply the principles shown at the next table. The principles have two levels, the main or overarching principle, and then 11 more detailed principles derived from the main one.

QA Main Principle for the Educational Programs
<p>Apply Academic QA standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At European Level, ESG: "Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG). (2015). Brussels, Belgium.", Part 1: Standards and guidelines for internal quality assurance https://ehea.info/page-standards-and-guidelines-for-quality-assurance. • At EIT Level, EIT QALE: EIT Quality Assurance and Learning Enhancement system (EIT QALE) described in the EIT Digital Handbook
QA Derived Principles
<p>Apply and extend the I&E Minor design structure, already checked against standards and refined over the years:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define General Learning Objectives (GLOs): A very general statement about the larger goals of the Master program or Learning Path in the Self-Standing on-line Modules 2. Define Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs): observable and measurable terms what a student is able to do as a result of completing the program or Learning Path 3. Define GLO's and OLOs reflecting the needs of the labour market in AI and the specific needs in relation to future applications of Emotion AI technology. 4. Describe the Master program in terms of a hierarchy of modules, not courses, with flexible ranges of ECTS to facilitate the organization and matching of courses within each university 5. For each module describe Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs): define what a learner will have acquired and will be able to do upon successfully completing their studies. ILOs should be expressed from the students' perspective and are measurable, achievable and assessable. 6. Use common templates for the I&E Minor, Technical Major and Self-Standing on-line Modules for the description of the modules <p>Apply and extend the QALE model's set of quality indicators:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Create Quality Indicators specific to the I&E Minor 8. Create Quality Indicators specific to the Technical Major

9. Create Quality Indicators specific to the Master Programme as a whole, transversal to the major and minor
10. Create Quality Indicators specific to the Self-Standing On-line Modules as a whole, transversal to all
11. Create Quality Indicators specific to each Self-Standing on-line Module

The principles were agreed with all partners in the Town-Hall meeting celebrated on June 12th, 2024. The next section will describe why we selected those principles and how we applied them during 2024.

4.2 ESG and EIT QALE standards

The main principle used to ensure the quality of the academic activities of WP1 and WP2, is to follow and comply with the guidelines indicated in the EIT Quality Assurance and Learning Enhancement system (EIT QALE) described in the EIT Digital Handbook, and in the "*Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG). (2015). Brussels, Belgium.*", Part 1: Standards and guidelines for internal quality assurance <https://ehea.info/page-standards-and-guidelines-for-quality-assurance>.

The ESG are a set of standards and guidelines for internal and external quality assurance in higher education. The ESG are not standards for quality, nor do they prescribe how the quality assurance processes are implemented, but they provide guidance, covering the areas which are vital for successful quality provision and learning environments in higher education.

The ESG apply to all higher education offered in the EHEA regardless of the mode of study or place of delivery. Thus, the ESG are also applicable to all higher education including transnational and cross-border provision.

The ESG was used at the EIT Digital Master School to create the EIT Quality Assurance and Learning Enhancement system (EIT QALE) described in the EIT Digital Handbook. A system that was fully developed for the I&E Minor included in all masters delivered at the that EIT Digital Master School, and that our EMAI4 master also includes.

The ESG-EIT QALE was developed, refined and improved for a decade, so we decided to extend its principles from the I&E Minor to the technical major of the master, Academic QA activities related to WP1, and to the Self standing learning Modules QA activities related to WP2. This goal is contemplated by subprinciples 1-6, and monitored by subprinciples 7-11.

4.2.1 QA aspects covered by ESG and EIT QALE

The QA aspect covered by ESG-EIT QALE are the following:

- A) Design and approval of programmes

- Programmes

- are designed with overall programme objectives that are in line with the institutional strategy and have explicit intended learning outcomes;
- are designed by involving students and other stakeholders in the work;
- benefit from external expertise and reference points;
- are designed so that they enable smooth student progression;
- define the expected student workload, e.g. in ECTS;
- include well-structured placement opportunities where appropriate;
- are subject to a formal institutional approval process.

B) Student-centred learning, teaching and assessment

- The implementation of student-centred learning and teaching

- respects and attends to the diversity of students and their needs, enabling flexible learning paths;
- considers and uses different modes of delivery, where appropriate;
- flexibly uses a variety of pedagogical methods;
- regularly evaluates and adjusts the modes of delivery and pedagogical methods;
- encourages a sense of autonomy in the learner, while ensuring adequate guidance and support from the teacher;
- promotes mutual respect within the learner-teacher relationship;
- has appropriate procedures for dealing with students' complaints

- Assessment:

Considering the importance of assessment for the students' progression and their future careers, quality assurance processes for assessment take into account the following:

- Assessors are familiar with existing testing and examination methods and receive support in developing their own skills in this field;
- The criteria for and method of assessment as well as criteria for marking are published in advance;
- The assessment allows students to demonstrate the extent to which the intended learning outcomes have been achieved. Students are given feedback, which, if necessary, is linked to advice on the learning process;
- Where possible, assessment is carried out by more than one examiner;
- The regulations for assessment take into account mitigating circumstances;
- Assessment is consistent, fairly applied to all students and carried out in accordance with the stated procedures;
- A formal procedure for student appeals is in place.

C) Student admission, progression, recognition and certification

It is vital to have fit-for-purpose admission, recognition and completion procedures, particularly when students are mobile within and across higher education systems.

It is important that access policies, admission processes and criteria are implemented consistently and in a transparent manner.

D) Information management

Effective processes to collect and analyse information should be established. The following are of interest:

- Key performance indicators;
- Profile of the student population;
- Student progression, success and drop-out rates;
- Students' satisfaction with their programmes;
- Learning resources and student support available;
- Career paths of graduates.

E) Public information

Institutions provide information about their activities, including the programmes they offer and the selection criteria for them, the intended learning outcomes of these programmes, the qualifications they award, the teaching, learning and assessment procedures used the pass rates and the learning opportunities available to their students as well as graduate employment information.

F) On-going monitoring and periodic review of programmes

Regular monitoring, review and revision of study programmes aim to ensure that the provision remains appropriate and to create a supportive and effective learning environment for students.

They include the evaluation of:

- The content of the programme in the light of the latest research in the given discipline thus ensuring that the programme is up to date;
- The changing needs of society;
- The students' workload, progression and completion;
- The effectiveness of procedures for assessment of students;
- The student expectations, needs and satisfaction in relation to the programme;
- The learning environment and support services and their fitness for purpose for the programme.

All those aspects are contemplated under subprinciples 7-11, via Quality Indicators.

4.2.2 QA and Learning Outcomes

EIT QALE's subprinciples 2, 3, and 5 focus on Learning Outcomes, which are defined as written statements detailing what a learner is expected to know, understand, and/or be able to do by the end of a learning period. Why incorporate Learning Outcomes in our QA process?

Firstly, they are explicitly mentioned in ESG (1.2 Design and approval of programmes). Secondly, they significantly aid in program design. This was emphasized by the European Network for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) during a workshop titled "Quality Assurance and Learning Outcomes" held in September 2010 in Vienna, Austria³. The workshop explored stakeholders' expectations from quality assurance agencies regarding learning outcome orientation. It discussed the opportunities and challenges of learning outcome orientation in higher education from various international perspectives. The workshop aimed to define the role of learning outcomes in external quality assurance and how they should be considered within its scope.

The workshop highlighted that student-centered learning and learning outcomes will be central to implementing the Bologna Process now and in the near future. The importance of learning outcomes will increase for several reasons. Firstly, they make qualifications more transparent for students. Secondly, as the range of graduates broadens, learning outcomes help employers better understand the acquired knowledge, skills, and competences, aiding in the recruitment of suitable candidates. Learning outcomes also enhance quality assurance by increasing transparency and comparability between qualification standards. Finally, they are valuable for course design.

The last benefit, the value of using Learning Outcomes as a tool for course design, is why subprinciples 2, 3, and 5 were adopted. As noted at the ENQA workshop, learning outcomes are excellent tools to ensure:

- The program meets subject-specific and academic and/or professional requirements.
- The program is coherent and not just a collection of disconnected knowledge, skills, and competences.

These aspects were deemed crucial for the project, especially in a new or emerging field like Emotional AI, where no similar master's program exists for reference.

In the following sections we will use the following terms:

- General Learning Objectives (GLOs): a very general statement about the larger goals of the Master program or Learning Path in the Self-Standing On-line Modules.
- Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs): observable and measurable terms what a student is able to do as a result of completing the Master program or Learning Path in the Self-Standing On-line Modules.
- Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs): clear, specific statements that describe what students are expected to know, do, or value by the end of a module of the Master program or Learning Path in the Self-Standing On-line Modules. ILOs make it easier to design assessments that

³ <https://www.enqa.eu/publications/quality-assurance-and-learning-outcomes/>

accurately measure student learning. They provide a basis for giving meaningful feedback, helping students understand their progress and areas for improvement.

4.3 QA aspects covered in 2024 in WP1

From all aspects described in 4.2.2, for WP1 and during 2024 the project focused on:

- A) Design and approval of programmes
- B) Student-centred learning, teaching and assessment

QA designed a series of templates to be filled out by the programme designers, and a series of Quality Indicators, all related to the above aspects.

4.3.1 WP1 QA Templates

The templates were developed as an internal QA tool (not to be published) to collect information and evidence ensuring that the program's design aligns with the principles in section 4.1 and 4.2, which focus on new or emerging program designs. Additionally, the templates aimed to encourage partners to consider the program design through the lens of learning outcomes, as highlighted in the latter part of section 4.2.2.

The templates were derived from the module descriptions of the I&E minor, which, as indicated in section 4.1, adhere to the ESG-EIT QALE standard.

Below is the template for the description of the Technical Major. It includes information on the General Learning Objectives (GLOs) and the Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs), and their relationship with the various modules of the program. The resulting GLOs and OLOs are described in D1.1, section 2 Curriculum design.

The modules are also defined, and the student's workload in ETCS. It also describes the progression that the students should follow through the modules. This information is also described in D1.1, section 2 Curriculum design.

TECHNICAL MAJOR		
General Learning Objectives (GLOs)		
Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs)		
OLO	Description	
Modules Description		
Module	Description	ECTS
Module Progression		

Module	Year	Semester	Prerequisites	

Mapping of the GLOs and OLOs on the Technical modules				
General Learning Objectives (GLOs)	MODULE 1	MODULE 2	...	MODULE N

Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs)	MODULE 1	MODULE 2	...	MODULE N

The second template is used to collect information about each module of the program. It includes details on the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) and their mapping to the Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs). Additionally, it provides information on the module contents, teaching and learning methods, and assessment and grading procedures.

Name of Module:	Credit Points (ECTS):	Module-ID:			
Person Responsible for Module (Name, Mail address):					
University:	Department:				
1. Prerequisites for Participation					
2. Intended Learning Outcomes					
ILO1:					
ILO2:					
...					
OLOS	ILO1	ILO2	ILO3	ILO4	ILO5
3. Content					
4. Teaching and Learning Methods					

5. Assessment and Grading Procedures

Both templates gather information corresponding to principles 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 and partially principle 3, "*Define GLO's and OLOs reflecting the needs of the labour market in AI and the specific needs in relation to future applications of Emotion AI technology*". The information regarding specifically to the link of OLOs and the market needs will be gathered from D1.1 Market Analysis and Curriculum Design.

The QA Team participated in most of the WP1 meetings to assist and guide partners on how to complete the templates. As anticipated, the task of gathering and organizing information for the templates encouraged partners to reflect on the program's design and organization, leading to the adoption of good practices such as:

- Enhancing program coherence
- Optimizing the courses organization
- Analysing the market to meet its needs

One major challenge in designing a new program is justifying its alignment with market needs. Attempting to do this through a simple list of courses and contents is often complex and unsatisfactory. However, using learning outcomes (OLOs and ILOs) makes the mapping between the program and market needs much clearer and more satisfactory.

4.3.2 WP1 Quality Control and Monitoring: The Quality Indicators

The control and monitoring of WP1 was done using and extending the ESG-EIT QALE standard's set of quality indicators:

- Quality Indicators specific to the Master Programme as a whole, transversal to the major and minor
- Quality Indicators specific to the Technical Major
- Quality Indicators specific to the I&E Minor

The quality indicators refer to aspects to be monitored and checked to verify that the programme is compliant with the ESG-EIT QALE standard.

The programme inherits and uses the I&E Minor from the master's programmes at EIT Digital Master School, so that part is already fully compliant with the standard.

For the other two sets of indicators, that are shown below, we used and extended the ESG-EIT QALE standard's set of quality indicators. Deliverables and the filled templates of the previous section were the main source of information. The checklist presented at this table covers only the indicators related to the activities that were planned to do during 2024. The list will include in the future other indicators related to

tasks to be developed in the following years, for example those related to the programme delivery, ECTS recognition, admission process, etc.

QA CHECKLIST			
MASTER PROGRAMME			
ECTS and recognition			
Indicator Source	Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
Application, selection and admission			
Indicator Source	Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
University and non-academic partner curriculum collaboration			
Indicator Source	Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
EIT Label 2.1.2 (adapted to match Principle 3)	Are non-academic partners engaged or consulted in the development of the programme curriculum, to meet the needs of the labour market in AI and the specific needs in relation to future applications of Emotion AI technology?	YES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey described at D1.1, Section 1 Market Analysis D1.1 Section 1.5 The impact of market analysis on curriculum development WP1 QA Templates (GLOs and OLOs)
EIT Label 2.2.2	Does the programme adopt a transdisciplinary approach which brings together science/technology knowledge in order to address broad societal and global challenges and/or link up with new business and innovation processes?	YES	The definition of the I&E Minor
On-going monitoring and periodic review of programmes			
Indicator Source	Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
EIT Label 4.3.1	Are other stakeholders (labour market, policy makers, etc.) given the opportunity to express their views of the programme on a	YES	Survey described at D1.1, Section 1 Market Analysis

	regular basis through a formal appraisal process?		
Public information			
Indicator Source	Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
ESG 1.8 Public information	Does the consortium provide information about their activities, including the programmes they offer and the selection criteria for them, the intended learning outcomes of these programmes, the qualifications they award, the teaching, learning and assessment procedures used, the pass rates and the learning opportunities available to their students as well as graduate employment information?	Partial YES since the program was not delivered yet	https://masterschool.eitdigital.eu/emotion-ai
TECHNICAL MAJOR			
Indicator Source	Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
ESG 1.2 Design and approval of programmes	Is it clearly defined the expected student workload (ECTS) for the major?	YES	WP1 QA Templates
ESG 1.2 Design and approval of programmes	Does the program include a definition of General Learning Objectives (GLOs) for the major?	YES	WP1 QA Templates
ESG 1.2 Design and approval of programmes	Does the program include a definition of Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs) for the major?	YES	WP1 QA Templates
EIT Label 1.3.1	Are the intended learning outcomes of the programme assessable, that is, with clear descriptions of skills and competencies rather than just content knowledge?	YES	WP1 QA Templates
EIT Label 1.4.2	Are the assessment tasks of the programme given to the students fit for purpose in relation to form (i.e. content-, competence or impact-based, depending on the ILO as this relates to the major's OLOs?	YES	WP1 QA Templates

EIT Label 1.5.2	Are assessment criteria (grade descriptors) used when assessing and grading student work from the programme related to the major's OLOs?	YES	WP1 QA Templates
EIT Label 1.6.2	Are teaching and learning methods of the programme aligned so that they are appropriate for achieving the intended learning outcomes of the major?	YES	WP1 QA Templates

4.4 Self-Standing Learning Modules QA

To maintain the quality in the development of the Self-Standing Learning Modules (SSLMs) in WP2, which have different online formats and objectives compared to the Master's modules, the Quality Manager (QM) and the WP2 leader collaborated to create a set of QA guidelines. A couple of decisions were taken:

- To assure the quality of the design of the online modules, the standard to follow will be ESG-EIT QALE standard, as in section 4.3, and as specified in the QA Principles agreed.
- To assure the quality in the production and development of the online modules, a guideline like the EIT Digital's "Guidelines and Best Practices for Online Courses" (November 2023) will be used for best practices. That guide, developed during the years by EIT Digital after creating hundreds of SSLMs, covers very important aspects like:
 - o Planning and Preparation
 - o Course Structure
 - o Content Creation
 - o Interactivity and Engagement
 - o Assessment and Evaluation

Two types of documents (not to be published) were created following those guidelines: templates for gathering information regarding the design and the production of the SSLMs, and a quality indicators checklist to monitor their implementation. The templates were based on the templates used for WP1. The quality indicators checklist is used to ensure that the objectives outlined in the project proposal are being met through the generation of the SSLMs. Section 4.4.1 and 4.4.2 will describe them.

4.4.1 WP2 QA Templates

The template for gathering information about the entire set of SSLMs is shown in the following table. As previously mentioned, it is similar to the one used for the Technical Major and includes a definition of Learning

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Paths. These Learning Paths are structured sequences of modules designed to lead to a certification, as outlined in the proposal.

It is important to note that the General Learning Objectives (GLOs) of the SSLMs differ from those of the Master's program. One of the goals, as described in the proposal, is to allow higher education institutions to incorporate teaching content from other institutions, potentially from different countries, into their own curricula. This approach aims to increase the diversity and attractiveness of the courses offered within the EMAI4EU master's program. Additionally, the SSLMs are intended to be accessible to external participants, such as professionals already in the job market who are looking to acquire new skills in the short term and pursue certification after completing a Learning Path.

SET OF SELF-STANDING MODULES				
General Learning Objectives (GLOs)				
GLO		Description		
Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs)				
OLO		Description		
Self-standing modules description				
ID	Module	Description		ECTS
1				
2				
3				
...				
N				
Self-standing module Progression				
LEARNING PATH 1				
Step	Module	Year	Month/s	Prerequisites
1				
2				
3				
4				
LEARNING PATH 2				
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
LEARNING PATH 3				
1				

2					
...					
N					
Mapping of the GLOs					
General Learning Objectives (GLOs)	MODULE 1	MODULE 2	MODULE 3	...	MODULE N
Mapping of the OLOs					
Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs)	MODULE 1	MODULE 2	...	MODULE N	

The Template for gathering information about each SSLM, is shown in the next table. The difference from the Master's module template of section 4.3.1 is that it includes:

- A section for the definition of the target audience (internal or external participants with or without a profile)
- A section to specify if the module is included as part of the Master
- A section to specify if the module is part of a Learning Path
- A Schedule, describing the course agenda and dates, including synchronous (sessions where there is interaction with the teacher(s)) and asynchronous sessions (sessions where there is no interaction with the teacher(s)).

Name of Module:	Credit Points (ECTS):	Module-ID:
Person Responsible for module (Name, Mail address):		
University:	Department:	
1. Short description of the module		
2. Target audience		

3. The self-standing module is included in the following course/s of the Master's program (If not, add the text "N/A")

--

4. Prerequisites for Participation (If not, add the text "N/A")

--

5. The self-standing module belongs to the following Learning path/s (If not, add the text "N/A")

--

6. Intended Learning Outcomes

ILO	Description

OLO	ILO1	ILO2	ILO3	ILO4	ILO5
	X	X			
			X		
					X

7. Teaching and Learning Methods

--

8. Structure (content, lessons, etc.)

Sessions	Descriptions, Content and materials

9. Schedule (course agenda and dates, including synchronous and asynchronous sessions)

--

Delivery	Sessions (in chronological order)	Hours	Dates	Total 25 hours (1 ECTS) / 50 hours (2 ECTS)
Asynchronous				Number of hours in ASYNC delivery: X
Synchronous				Number of hours in SYNC delivery: X
11. Assessment and Grading Procedures (describe the passing Threshold used)				
12. Description about how can successfully complete the module to obtain the certificate (needs to be done in your self-standing module to obtain the certificate)				

4.4.2 WP2 Quality Control and Monitoring: The Quality Indicators

The control and monitoring of WP2 will be done using and extending the ESG-EIT QALE standard's set of quality indicators, which will refer to aspects to be monitored and checked to verify that the programme is compliant with the ESG-EIT QALE standard.

The checklist will be divided in the following 6 sections:

- General self-standing module set questions. General questions to assess quality indicators are included here, such as: "Does the program include a definition of General Learning Objectives (GLOs) for the set of self-standing modules?" or "Have common templates been used for the design of all resources necessary for the self-standing modules (for slides, video creation, etc.)?"
- Specific self-standing module – main questions. This section checks that relevant information, such as the target audience or questions of importance like this: "Are the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) of the module assessable, that is, with clear descriptions of skills and competencies rather than just content knowledge?"
- Specific self-standing module - course structure questions. This section is dedicated to checking what has been taken into account when defining the structure of the course: schedule, synchronous and asynchronous sessions, is the work well balanced, etc.
- Specific self-standing module - assessment and certification questions. Section dedicated to evaluating the assessment methods used, as well as the certification obtained.
- Specific self-standing module - other questions. This is a section dedicated to questions that were not classified in previous sections, such as: "Is the module descriptor accessible to students?"
- Delivery of self-standing modules. This last section is dedicated to the assessment of everything related to the delivery of SSMLs, such as: "Is there a single digital learning platform for all modules that allows modules to be available for any country in Europe?" or "Is the platform where all the modules are located managed and coordinated by EITD?"

The following is a draft of the checklist that will be used (subject to review).

SSLM QUALITY CHECKLIST		
1. GENERAL SELF-STANDING MODULE SET QUESTIONS		
Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
1.1 Does the program include a definition of General Learning Objectives (GLOs) for the set of self-standing modules?	YES/NO	A table defining the GLOs, and a GLO Coverage table mapping how the GLOs are linked to the set of modules
1.2 Does the program include a definition of Overarching Learning Outcomes (OLOs) for the set of self-standing modules?	YES/NO	A table defining the OLOs, and a OLO Coverage table mapping how the GLOs are linked to the set of modules
1.3. Are there at least 11 self-standing modules on Data Science and AI developed and delivered?	YES/NO	List of the self-standing modules with the detail about the area of knowledge (Data Science)

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1.4. Are there at least 2 self-standing modules on Innovation and Entrepreneurship or Ethics developed and delivered?	YES/NO	List of the I&E and/or Ethics self-standing modules
1.5. Is there at least one partner responsible for each self-standing module?	YES/NO	List of responsible for each self-standing module
1.6. Are all self-standing modules at least in English?	YES/NO	Some evidence is shown to support the claim.
1.7. Has a common guideline or best practices been used for the design of all self-standing modules?	YES/NO	Document with the common guidelines or best practices used
1.8. Have common templates been used for the design of all resources necessary for the self-standing modules (for slides, video creation, etc.)?	YES/NO	The templates used
1.9. Have at least 2 certification schemes been defined for self-standing modules (ECTS schema, Coursera certificate, EIT Digital certificate, etc.)?	YES/NO	Certification schemes definition
1.10. Has it been considered that each certification includes at least something about I&E and ethics?	YES/NO	Certification schemes definition
2. SPECIFIC SELF-STANDING MODULE – MAIN QUESTIONS		
Quality Indicator	Answer	Evidence
2.1 Are the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) of the module assessable, that is, with clear descriptions of skills and competencies rather than just content knowledge?	YES/NO	Description of modules/courses with ILOs highlighted including description of skills and competencies and mapping to the OLOs
2.2. Is the self-standing module included in any course of the Master's program?	YES/NO	A table indicating the courses where the self-standing module is included modules
2.4 Is the target audience is identified?	YES/NO	Target audience definition in template
3. SPECIFIC SELF-STANDING MODULE - COURSE STRUCTURE QUESTIONS		
3.1. Is structure of self-standing module (lessons, etc.) designed to assure that the students will achieve the ILOs defined for the module?	YES/NO	Course structure of your self-standing module
3.2. Is there a definition of the module's schedule (course agenda and dates, including synchronous and asynchronous sessions)?	YES/NO	Schedule of the self-standing module
3.3. Has a balance between synchronous and asynchronous sessions been defined in your course? (modules should include an asynchronous portion in an online format that participants can follow at their own pace, including online lectures, exercises and business challenges, etc.).	YES/NO	Synchronous and asynchronous sessions of the self-standing module

3.4. Is it clearly defined the expected student workload for the self-standing module?	YES/NO	A table with each of the parts' (lessons, etc.) description and a table with the student's progression
4. SPECIFIC SELF-STANDING MODULE - ASSESSMENT AND CERTIFICATION QUESTIONS		
5.1. Are the assessment tasks of the programme given to the students fit for purpose in relation to form (i.e. content-, competence or impact-based, depending on the ILO?	YES/NO	Assessment method used connected to the ILO, and passing rules
5.2. Is it defined how can successfully complete the module to obtain the certificate?	YES/NO	Description of the requirements to obtain the certificate
5.3. Has the module completion certificate been issued jointly by the EITD and the higher education institution coordinating the module?	YES/NO	A template of the module completion certification document must be provided, where it can be clearly seen that the certificate is issued jointly by the EITD and the higher education institution that coordinates the corresponding module.
5.4. As part of specific learning paths that offer participants the possibility of obtaining a certification at the end of the learning path, have certification schemes been developed by EMAI4EU partners that involve the following? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mandatory completion of a specific set of modules, • a final certification exam composed of a theoretical exam and a practical exam. 	YES/NO	Certification schemes generated by EMAI4EU partners must be provided. In particular, EMAI4EU partners envisage to develop 2 certification schemes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the entry-level certifications will target people without a degree or considerable knowledge and work experience in the domain of Data Science and Artificial Intelligence, • the expert-level certifications will target people with a degree in Computer Science and similar fields or with significant work experience in the areas.
5. SPECIFIC SELF-STANDING MODULE - OTHER QUESTIONS		
6.1. Is the module descriptor accessible to students?	YES/NO	Webpage link
6.2. Is there a welcome video for the module?	YES/NO	Webpage link
6. DELIVERY OF SELF-STANDING MODULES		
7.1. Is there a single digital learning platform for all modules that allows modules to be available for any country in Europe?	YES/NO	The URL of the e-learning platform where all the modules are available is provided.

7.2. Is the platform where all the modules are located managed and coordinated by EITD?	YES/NO	Some evidence is shown to support the claim.
7.3. Is registration for EMAI4EU autonomous learning modules as simple as possible for participants (registration for all courses is possible through a single registration page / single enrolment portal)?	YES/NO	Some evidence is shown to support the claim (screenshots, URL, etc.).
7.4. Is the registration portal located on the same platform where the courses are available?	YES/NO	Some evidence is shown to support the claim (screenshots, URL, etc.).
7.5. Has a Module Manager been assigned for each module who is responsible for evaluating the application to the modules and coordinating with the teachers involved the live classes and the grading of the exercises?	YES/NO	Some evidence is shown to support the claim.
7.6. Have specific month-long periods (i.e., in January and May of each year) been made available for participants who have successfully completed the required online modules to take the certification exams? (during the one-month period, multiple dates must be made available to participants to take the certification exams)	YES/NO	Some evidence is shown to support the claim.